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NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOUR OF FOAM CORED CURVED SANDWICH PANELS SUBJECTED TO THERMO-MECHANICAL LOADING

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SUMMARY

The non-linear analysis of curved composite sandwich panels with a compliant foam core subjected to combined thermal and mechanical loading is considered. It is shown that the response remains linear when only thermal loading is involved, whereas the response becomes strongly non-linear with limit point behaviour when mechanical loading is applied at elevated temperatures.

Keywords: Curved sandwich panels, thermo-mechanical loading, degradation of core properties, nonlinear response

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Polymeric foam cored sandwich structures are being used increasingly for a variety of applications including wind turbine blades, boat hulls and ship structures as well as for structural applications in the transportation and aerospace sectors. Sandwich structures are often subjected to aggressive service conditions which may include elevated temperatures [1]. Polymeric foam core materials are particularly sensitive to elevated temperatures, as significant degradation of the mechanical properties may occur well within the operating range of temperatures. For example, PVC foams (Divinycell® and Airex®, [2,3]) lose all stiffness and strength at about 80-100°C, while PMI foams (Polymethacrylimide, eg Rohacell® [4]) lose the heat distortion resistance at about 200°C. Moreover, significant degradation of the properties occurs at much lower temperatures than the temperatures where a complete loss of stiffness and strength is experienced.

A large variety of analytical and numerical models are available for sandwich structures (beams, plates and shells). This includes classical sandwich models, Zenkert [1] and Noor et al. [5], for sandwich panels with anti-plane cores. These models are usually based on the “equivalent single layer” approach (ESL approach), where the layered sandwich structure is represented by a solid homogeneous panel with equivalent homogenized properties.

Buckling, post-buckling and non-linear analyses associated with thermally induced deformation in laminated composite and sandwich panels have been attempted using various first and high-order shear deformable models together with analytical/closed-form or finite element solutions; see Ko [6], Kant and Babu [7], Lanhe [8] and Tessler *et. al.* [9], ignoring the temperature dependent core properties.

Several researchers have used high-order theories to model the thermo-mechanical response of laminated or sandwich panels including Najafizadeh and Heydari [10], Shiau and Kuo [11] and Matsunaga [12]. However, none of these have included the core through-thickness flexibility.

A more comprehensive approach is the so-called high-order sandwich panel theory (HSAPT), which models the layered sandwich panel as composed of two face sheets and a core material that are interconnected through the equilibrium and compatibility conditions, and which incorporate the through-thickness flexibility of the core. HSAPT has been successfully used in several studies, including hygrothermal effects, buckling (global and local) and nonlinear response, see Frostig *et al.* [13-17].

More recently, Frostig and Thomsen have studied thermal buckling and post-buckling of foam cored sandwich structures by adopting the HSAPT approach, and by assuming core properties that are either temperature independent [18] or temperature dependent [19]. The HSAPT formulation was extended to include geometrical nonlinearity and simultaneous mechanical and thermal loads [20]. The models presented in [18, 19] were extended to include free vibrations with temperature dependent core properties [21, 22]. The research reported in [18-22] has shown that thermal degradation (softening) of polymer foam core materials exert a significant influence on the performance of flat sandwich panels/plates. More specifically, the degradation of the core properties with rising temperature lowers the buckling resistance [18, 19] and the panel eigenfrequencies [21,22]. In addition, when external mechanical loads act simultaneously with thermal loads, the material degradation may shift the response from being linear and stable into being nonlinear and unstable [20]. This is especially pronounced when thermal gradients are present across the sandwich panel thickness, and when the heated face is subject to compressive loading/stresses [20].

MODELLING AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

The work presented herein presents an extension of the work presented in [18-22] in that it considers the non-linear analysis of curved composite sandwich panels with a compliant foam core subjected to combined thermal and mechanical loading. Thus, a HSAPT model developed for curved panels, see Frostig [25], which includes the through-thickness core flexibility as well as geometrical non-linearity, is further expanded to accommodate for the thermo-mechanical effects. The full details of this work can be found in Frostig and Thomsen [23,24].

Mathematical Formulation

In the mathematical formulation the sandwich panel is modeled as two curved faces that are interconnected through compatibility and equilibrium with a 2-D compliant/deformable elastic core with shear and radial (through-thickness) normal

stress resistance. The HSAPT model for the curved sandwich panel is based on the following restrictive assumptions:

- The curved face sheets possess in-plane (circumferential) and bending stiffnesses, and they obey kinematic relations corresponding to an intermediate class of deformations (small strains and moderate rotations (as defined by Brush and Almroth [26]), and negligible shear deformations.
- The core is considered as a 2D linear elastic continuum obeying small deformation kinematic relations, and where the core height may change and the section plane does not remain plane after deformation.
- The core is further assumed to possess shear and radial normal stiffness only; whereas the in-plane (circumferential) normal stiffness is assumed negligible. Accordingly, the longitudinal normal stresses are assumed to be nil, full bonding between the face sheets and the core is assumed, the interfacial layers can resist shear as well as radial normal stresses, and the loads are applied to the face sheets only.

Figure 1 shows the geometry/dimensions, temperature distribution, sign conventions and the external loads. Figure 2 shows the internal stress resultants and stresses.

Figure 1. Dimensions, temperature distribution and signs conventions of a curved sandwich panel: (a) geometry; (b) loads at face sheets.

The derivation of the mathematical formulation is mathematical model is lengthy and complex and is thus omitted herein. Instead reference is given to [23, 24] for full details. Thus, [23] includes the mathematical formulation that presents the field and governing equations, the appropriate boundary conditions and the thermal fields within the core assuming that the mechanical core properties are temperature independent (*TI*). Furthermore, Ref. [24] presents the general solution for the core stress and displacement fields when the core properties are coordinate dependent in the radial (through-thickness) direction as a result of the temperature dependence (*TD*) of the mechanical core properties. Ref. [24] also contains the results of an extensive numerical study that investigates the non-linear response of sandwich panels with both *TI* and *TD* cores.

Figure 2. Internal stress resultants and core stresses in curved sandwich panel segment: (a) stress resultants on the deformed shape of the panel; (b) core stresses.

Figure 3. Geometry, dimensions, mechanical properties at 20 °C, imposed temperature distribution and boundary conditions of the investigated shallow curved panel.

Numerical Study – Curved Sandwich Panel Subjected to Distributed Loading and with Temperature Dependent Core Properties

Selected results of a numerical study is presented (see [24] for complete results) to illustrate the thermo-mechanical non-linear response of a simply-supported shallow curved sandwich panel subjected to a distributed load, see Fig. 3 for geometry,

dimensions, imposed temperature distribution and boundary conditions. The sandwich panel consists of two aluminum face sheets of a thickness of 1mm and a Divinycell HP60 PVC foam core with room temperature properties (20 °C) $E_c=56.7$ MPa and $G_c=22$ MPa and with a thickness of 25 mm. The temperature dependency of the E- and G-moduli of the Divinycell HP core material is specified in Fig. 4. The panel edges are reinforced by an edge beam and assumed to be bonded to the adjacent core, see Detail A in Fig. 3. The supporting system prevents circumferential displacement, and in this paper only results for simple support conditions (denoted *ssI*) are included.

Figure 4. Normalized temperature-dependent elastic and shear moduli of Divinycell HP and P foam core materials: (a) Divinycell HP foam, (b) Divinycell P foam. Legends: (E) – Modulus of elasticity, (G) – Shear modulus; [19, 20] based on [28, 29].

The combined thermal and mechanical loading response study outlines the behaviour of the curved sandwich panel when subjected to a distributed load that is below the limit point load levels. The imposed heating temperatures profile change from 20°C to 78°C and assuming a uniform temperature distribution.

The combined thermo-mechanical response of a simply-supported curved sandwich panel with a 1.7 kN/mm distributed load, which is about 90% of the corresponding limit point load level (with no thermal loading) [24], and uniform thermal loading at different temperature levels is shown in Figs. 5. The deformed shapes appear in Fig. 5a, and reveal quite small deformations with smooth displacements patterns and no signs of local buckling. The vertical displacements of the face sheets along half the circumference of the panel appear in Fig. 5b from which a significant growth of the displacements at the limit point temperature level of 27.72°C (see [24]) is observed. The bending moment diagrams reveal a ripple type patterns in the vicinity of the supports, see Figs. 5c. The interfacial shear stresses at the upper and the lower face-core interfaces, see Fig. 5d, yield large values in the vicinity of the edge as well at the quarter of the circumference/span. The trends of the interfacial radial normal stresses, see Fig. 5e, follow the same trends as those of the bending moments.

Figure 5. Thermo-mechanical response of face sheets along circumference of simply-supported panel with TD core properties when loaded by a fully distributed load applied at the upper face sheet and a uniform temperature distribution. (a) vertical displacements; (b) bending moments; and in upper and lower face-core interfaces: (c) shear stresses; (d) radial normal stresses Legend: _____ (thick) upper face/interface, _____ (thin) lower face/interface.

Figure 6: Equilibrium curves for thermo-mechanical loading of simply-supported curved sandwich panel with TD core properties and subjected to distributed load levels of different magnitude applied at the upper face sheet and a uniform temperature distribution. (a) vertical displacements of faces sheets; (b) bending moments in faces; (c) interfacial shear stress in upper interface; (d) interfacial radial normal stresses at face-core interfaces. Legend: black – upper face sheet, red – lower face sheet.

The effects of the magnitude of the distributed load on the equilibrium curves of the combined thermo-mechanical response of a simply-supported curved panel with uniform thermal loading at various temperatures are shown in Fig. 6. Curves displaying temperature vs. extreme values of the face sheet vertical displacements in Fig. 6a for the different load levels appear. At all load levels a limit point behavior is observed, and the temperature at which the limit point is reached is lowered as the magnitude of the distributed load is increased. It is also observed that the slope of the curves at the limit point approaches zero. It should be further noticed that up to the limit point temperature the displacements almost do not change with respect to the initial level (20 °C temperature), while in the near vicinity of the limit point temperature there is a

significant change (increase) of the displacements. With respect to the face sheet bending moment curves, see Fig. 6b, and the curves for the face-core interface radial normal stresses, see Fig. 6d, there is a gradual change between the initial values (no thermal loading) and the values at the limit point. With respect to the interfacial shear stresses at the upper face-core interface, see Fig. 6c, the values prior to the limit point reduce, and they are significantly increased at the limit point temperature level.

Reference is made to [24] with respect to results obtained for cases where a thermal gradient between the two face sheets is imposed. Generally, similar trends, as observed in Figs. 5 and 6 where uniform thermal distributions are imposed, are observed when thermal gradients are imposed between the faces with the highest temperature at the lower face sheet (see Fig. 3). However, this situation is generally more severe and the equilibrium curves show that responses are generally unstable for any value of the thermal gradient value [24].

CONCLUSIONS

The paper considers the thermally induced deformations of the polymeric foam core of a curved sandwich panel simultaneously subjected to thermal and mechanical loading. The analyses include the effects of the flexibility of the core in the radial (thickness) direction. The modeling was conducted using the HSAPT formulation including both temperature independent and dependent properties, see [23, 24] for full details.

The combined thermo-mechanical response with when the temperature dependence of the polymeric core properties is included (TD properties) is associated with a limit point behavior even at low temperature values. Thus, the degradation of the core properties yields a non-linear response with unstable limit point behavior, even though the stress and displacement fields induced by the thermal loads themselves in effect act opposite to those induced by the mechanical loads.

The effects of the load level on the combined thermo-mechanical response have been investigated for loads below the limit point level for the pure mechanical loading case. For the case of a distributed load, the response of a simply-supported curved sandwich panel displays an unstable limit point behavior with very similar limit point temperature values as a result of the initiation of local buckling in the compressed face sheet. Generally, as the load is increased the limit point temperature reduces.

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